

Proton-NMR Spectra of 3-Substituted Propynes and 1,4-Bis Derivatives of 2-Butyne

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¹H nmr data of several acetylenic derivatives are reported with full assignments. Substituent effects have been analysed.

The ¹³C and ¹H nmr chemical shifts of acetylenic compounds have been of interest to several research groups. The structural factors affecting the ¹³C nmr chemical shifts have been extensively investigated by several research groups including ourselves¹⁻¹⁰. Two of our recent communications deal with complete signal assignments in the ¹³C nmr spectra of 1,6-disubstituted-2,4-hexadiynes⁹, 3-substituted propynes and 1,4-disubstituted-2-butyne¹¹. The substituent chemical shifts (S.C.S.) have been determined and the various factors responsible for inducing these have been discussed.

The present communication reports the complete ¹H nmr assignments of the 3-substituted propynes and 1,4-bis derivatives of 2-butyne whose ¹³C nmr investigations have been reported in our previous communication²².

	R	R ¹	R ²	R ³	X	Y
1 ;	Cl	Cl	H	H	O	O
2 ;	Cl	Cl	Cl	Cl	OO	OO
3 ;	H	H	Cl	Cl	OO	OO
4 ;	Me	Me	H	H	OO	OO
5 ;	Me	Me	Me	Me	OO	O
6 ;	Cl	Cl	H	H	O	S
7 ;	Cl	Cl	Cl	H	O	S
8 ;	Cl	Cl	H	H	S	S
9 ;	H	H	H	H	NMe	NMe
10 ;	Cl	H	H	H	O	NMe
11 ;	Cl	H	Cl	H	O	NMe
12 ;	Cl	Cl	H	H	SO ₂	SO ₂
13 ;	Cl	Cl	H	H	O	SO
14 ;	Cl	Cl	H	H	O	SO ₂

	X
15 ;	O
16 ;	S
17 ;	NMe

Chart 1. Acetylenic compounds investigated.

Results and Discussion

The compounds chosen for the present investigation had substituents Ar-X- attached to the 1,4-positions of the 2-butyne and the 3-positions of propynes (Chart 1). These differed in the heteroatomic group (S, NMe, O, sulphone, sulphoxide) by which the substituent was attached to the acetylenic compound as well as in the substituent patterns of the aryl rings. The complete assignments were made from S.C.S., intercomparisons and investigation of coupling patterns. In certain cases where the complexity of the spectra were enhanced by second-order effects, the chemical shifts and coupling constants were determined to a high degree of precision by using the PANIC (Parameter Adjustments in Nmr by Iteration calculations) programme available in Bruker software; this is a minicomputer version of the LAOCOON programme. Differences between calculated and experimental values of positions of signals did not exceed the resolution in Hz/pt. All the proton assignments are collected in Table 1.

The overall conclusions regarding factors influencing ¹H nmr chemical shifts which could be drawn from an inspection of the ¹H nmr assignments (Table 1) are as follows :

(i) In CDCl₃ medium, the protons of the methylene group resonated between δ 4.6—4.8 (for O-Ar substituents), 4.0—4.1 (for-NMeAr), 3.6—3.7 (for S-Ar), 3.9 (for SO₂Ar) and 4.0 (for SOAr). Solvent shifts from CDCl₃ to DMSO-d₆ for these protons are small, being only significant for -SAr and -SO₂Ar substituents where downfield shifts of about 0.2 and 0.6 ppm respectively were observed.

(ii) The introduction of *para*-substituents had virtually no effect on the chemical shifts of the methylene protons. An *ortho*-chloro substituent, however, caused a very small but definite 0.1 ppm downfield shift of these protons.

(iii) The chemical shifts of the C-1 methylene protons are hardly affected by the nature of the C-4 hetero-substituent and vice versa.

(iv) When the C-1 and C-4 substituents are

TABLE 1—¹H NMR (300 MHz) ASSIGNMENTS OF PROTONS*

Cmopd. no.	H-C ₁	H-C ₄	H-C ₂ '	H-C ₃ '	H-C ₄ '	H-C ₅ '	H-C ₆ '	H-C ₂ "	H-C ₃ "	H-C ₄ '	H-C ₅ "	H-C ₆ "	Others
1b	4.69(s)	4.69(s)	6.85(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	7.25(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	—	7.25(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	6.85(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	6.85(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	7.25(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	—	7.25(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	6.85(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	—
1a,b	4.80(s)	4.80(s)	6.90(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	7.25(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	—	7.25(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	6.90(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	6.90(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	7.25(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	—	7.25(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	6.90(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	—
2c	4.78(s)	4:78(s)	—	7.38(d) <i>J</i> _m 2.5	—	7.12(dd) <i>J</i> _m 2.5 <i>J</i> _o 8.8	6.87(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.8	—	7.38(d) <i>J</i> _m 2.5	—	7.12(dd) <i>J</i> _m 2.5 <i>J</i> _o 8.8	6.87(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.8	—
3b	4.80(s)	4.80(s)	—	7.38(dd) <i>J</i> _m 1.6 <i>J</i> _o 7.9	6.94(td) <i>J</i> _m 1.6 <i>J</i> _o 8.2	7.17(td) <i>J</i> _m 1.4 <i>J</i> _o ~7.6	6.99(dd) <i>J</i> _m 1.4 <i>J</i> _o 8.3	—	7.38(dd) <i>J</i> _m 1.6 <i>J</i> _o 7.9	6.94(td) <i>J</i> _m 1.6 <i>J</i> _o 8.2	7.17(td) <i>J</i> _m 1.4 <i>J</i> _o ~7.6	6.99(dd) <i>J</i> _m 1.4 <i>J</i> _o 8.3	—
4b	4.72(s)	4.72(s)	6.88(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.4	7.11(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.4	—	7.11(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.4	6.88(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.4	6.88(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.4	7.11(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.4	—	7.11(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.4	6.88(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.4	CH ₃ 2.34(s)
4a,b	4.73(s)	4.73(s)	6.78 <i>J</i> _o 8.3	7.02 <i>J</i> _o 8.3	—	7.02 <i>J</i> _o 8.3	6.78 <i>J</i> _o 8.3	6.78 <i>J</i> _o 8.3	7.02 <i>J</i> _o 8.3	—	7.02 <i>J</i> _o 8.3	6.78(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.3	2.18(s)
5d	4.68(s)	4.68(s)	—	6.95 (brs)	—	6.91(dd) <i>J</i> _o 8.2 <i>J</i> _m 2.1	6.77(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.2	—	6.95 (brs)	—	6.91(dd) <i>J</i> _o 8.2 <i>J</i> _m 2.1	6.77(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.2	2.19(s) <i>p</i> -CH ₃ 2.26(s) <i>o</i> -CH ₃
6e	4.63(t) <i>J</i> 2.0	3.60(t) <i>J</i> 2.0	6.82(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	7.20(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	—	7.20(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	6.82(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	7.29(d) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.8	7.23(d) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.8	—	7.23(d) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.8	7.29(d) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.8	—
6a,e	4.72(t) <i>J</i> 2.2	3.86(t) <i>J</i> 2.2	6.86(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	7.24(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	—	7.24(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	6.86(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	7.29(s)	7.29(s)	—	7.29(s)	7.29(s)	—
7f	4.80(t) <i>J</i> 2.1	3.69(t) <i>J</i> 2.1	—	7.45(d) <i>J</i> _m 2.5	—	7.19(dd) <i>J</i> _m 2.5 <i>J</i> _o 8.8	6.93(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.8	7.34(AB-pattern) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.7	7.31(AB-pattern) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.7	—	7.31(AB-pattern) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.7	7.34(AB-pattern) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.7	—
8g	3.57(s)	3.57(s)	7.29(dd) ^m <i>J</i> _o 9.5 <i>J</i> _m 2.7	7.24(dd) ^m <i>J</i> _o 9.5 <i>J</i> _m 2.7	—	7.24(dd) ^m <i>J</i> _o 9.5 <i>J</i> _m 2.7	7.29(dd) ^m <i>J</i> _o 9.5 <i>J</i> _m 2.7	7.29(dd) ^m <i>J</i> _o 9.5 <i>J</i> _m 2.7	7.24(dd) ^m <i>J</i> _o 9.5 <i>J</i> _m 2.7	—	7.24(dd) ^m <i>J</i> _o 9.5 <i>J</i> _m 2.7	7.29(dd) ^m <i>J</i> _o 9.5 <i>J</i> _m 2.7	—
9h	3.98(s)	3.98(s)	6.80(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	7.24(brt) <i>J</i> _o ~8.5	6.78(d) <i>J</i> _o 7.7	7.24(brt) <i>J</i> _o ~8.5	6.80(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	6.80(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	7.24(brt) <i>J</i> _o ~8.5	6.78(d) <i>J</i> _o 7.7	7.24(brt) <i>J</i> _o ~8.5	6.80(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	2.86(s), N-Me
10i	4.66(t) <i>J</i> 1.8	4.11(t) <i>J</i> 1.8	6.88(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.8	7.25(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.8	—	7.25(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.8	6.88(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.8	6.85-6.89 (obs by 4',3',5')	7.32(t) <i>J</i> _o 7.3	6.85-6.89 (obs by 2',6')	7.32(t) <i>J</i> _o 7.3	6.85-6.89 (obs by 4',3',5')	—
11j	4.73(t) <i>J</i> 1.7	4.08(t) <i>J</i> 1.7	—	7.39(d) <i>J</i> _m 2.2	—	7.09(dd) <i>J</i> _o 7.7 <i>J</i> _m 2.2	6.85-6.89 (obs by 2'',6'',6')	6.83(d) <i>J</i> _o 7.9	7.28(t) <i>J</i> _o 7.9	6.85-6.89 (obs by 2'',6'',6')	7.28(t) <i>J</i> _o 7.9	6.83(d) <i>J</i> _o 7.9	2.93(s) N-Me
12g	3.92(s)	3.92(s)	7.58(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.5	7.92(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.5	—	7.92(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.5	7.58(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.5	7.58(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.5	7.92(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.5	—	7.58(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.5	7.92(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.5	—
13a	4.78(s)	4.02(s)	6.88(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	7.30(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	—	7.30(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	6.88(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.9	7.56(AB-pattern) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.5	7.65(AB-pattern) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.5	—	7.65(AB-pattern) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.5	7.56(AB-pattern) ^m <i>J</i> _o 8.5	—
14a,f	4.77(t) <i>J</i> 2.0	4.60(t) <i>J</i> 2.0	6.85(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	7.26(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	—	7.26(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	6.85(d) <i>J</i> _o 9.0	7.62(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.6	7.80(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.6	—	7.80(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.6	7.62(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.6	—
15k	4.65(d) <i>J</i> 2.3	2.50(t) <i>J</i> 2.3	7.01(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.0	7.3(t) <i>J</i> _o 8.0	~7.0 (obs by 2',6')	7.3(t) <i>J</i> _o 8.0	7.01(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
15a,k	4.76(d) <i>J</i> 2.3	3.46(d) <i>J</i> 2.3	6.92(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.2	7.21(t) <i>J</i> _o 8.2	~6.9 (obs by 2',6')	7.21(t) <i>J</i> _o 8.2	6.92(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.2	—	—	—	—	—	—
16l	3.55(d) <i>J</i> 2.6	2.20(t) <i>J</i> 2.6	7.42(d) <i>J</i> _o 7.3	7.28(brt) <i>J</i> _o 7.2	7.20(t) <i>J</i> _o 7.2	7.28(t) <i>J</i> _o 7.1	7.42(d) <i>J</i> _o 7.3	—	—	—	—	—	—
16a,l	3.77 (brs)	3.44 (brs)	7.40(d) <i>J</i> _o 7.4	7.31(brt) <i>J</i> ~7.3	7.20(t) <i>J</i> _o 7.2	7.31(t) <i>J</i> _o 7.3	7.4(d) <i>J</i> _o 7.4	—	—	—	—	—	—
17h	3.92(d) <i>J</i> 2.4	2.06(t) <i>J</i> 2.4	6.80(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.0	7.20(t,fs) <i>J</i> _o ~7.5	6.68(t) <i>J</i> _o ~7.2	7.2(t,fs) <i>J</i> _o ~7.5	6.8(d) <i>J</i> _o 8.0	—	—	—	—	—	—

* Chemical shifts (δ) in ppm and coupling constants (J) in Hz. ** Values recorded in CDCl₃, except for (a) where values refer to spectra recorded in DMSO-d₆. bRef. 11. cRef. 12 dRef. 13. eRef. 18. fRef. 14. gRef. 15. hRef. 21 iRef. 16. jRef. 17. kRef. 20. lRef. 19. mAssignments may be interchanged between 2', 6', 2'', 6'' and 3', 5', 3'', 5'' respectively

different each methylene group shows a finely split triplet with a coupling constant of about 2 Hz.

(v) The coupling information and chemical shifts for the aromatic protons are detailed in Table 1, the more complex among these have been calculated by the PANIC programme.

(vi) For compounds 15, 16 and 17, coupling constants between the acetylenic and the methylene protons varied from 2.3 to 2.6 Hz.

Experimental

All compounds (Table 1) were prepared according to literature procedures¹¹⁻²¹. They gave the expected elemental analyses and ir spectra. The ¹H nmr spectra were recorded with spectrum widths of about 8–10 ppm with a resolution of 0.3–0.45 Hz/point. Pulse widths varied from 6–7 μs corresponding to flip angles of 70–80°. Relaxation delays of 2.0–2.5 s corresponding to pulse repetition rates of 4–5 s were used. Spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ or DMSO-d₆ and referenced to tetramethylsilane.

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